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Abstract	<p>This deliverable reports the work achieved during the first phase of the AD4GD project concerning the Internet of Things data. It presents the methodology, data models, and tools to be applied to the pilots' IoT data in the second part of the project. Special emphasis was on Internet of Things (IoT) data streams and standard protocols. A list of requirements for IoT for the three pilots of the AD4GD project is presented. The aspects linked to the IoT were considered in the proposed architecture for the intended Green Deal Data Space. Several components related to IoT data management have been added to the GDDS architecture, such as an NGINX proxy server, a FROST-OGC SensorThings API server, FIWARE context brokers, and a TM Forum IoT server. The APIs and the corresponding data models are presented in this report for each service installed in the IoT Lab research infrastructure. A mapping between different data models was realised to facilitate the interoperability and the integration of the heterogeneous sources of IoT data. For pilot 1, some tools were developed to push data generated by IoT sensors deployed in a small lake in the Berlin region. For pilot 2, the description and the use of the camera traps in the biodiversity are explained. For pilot 3, IoT air quality sensor data and its management is described. The Simpl initiative was analysed and its risk to the finalisation of the GDDS reported. The use of edge computing next to the IoT sensor is compared with the implementation of IoT and HPC.</p>
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ABBREVIATIONS

Abbreviation	Definition
AI	Artificial Intelligence
API	Application Programming Interface
CAMS	Copernicus Atmosphere Monitoring Service
CTMS	Camera Trap Metadata Standard
CRUD	Create, Read, Update and Delete
CSIRT	Computer Security Incident Response Team
CSV	Comma-Separated Values
FAIR	Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability and Reusability
GDDS	Green Deal Data Space
GUI	Graphical User Interface
HPC	High-Performance Computing
HTTP	Hypertext Transfer Protocol
HTTPS	Hypertext Transfer Protocol Secure
IDSAs	International Data Spaces Association
IoT	Internet of Things
JSON	JavaScript Object Notation
JSON-LD	JavaScript Object Notation-Linked Data
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
ML	Machine Learning

MQTT	Message Queue Telemetry Transport
NGSI-LD	Next Generation Service Interfaces Linked Data
NGSI-v2	Next Generation Service Interfaces version 2
O&M	Observations and Measurements
OGC	Open Geospatial Consortium
OWL	Web Ontology Language
PaaS	Platform as a Service
REST	Representational State Transfer
STA	SensorThings API
STApplus	SensorThings API plus
SWE	Sensor Web Enablement
TDWG	Biodiversity Information Standards
URL	Uniform Resource Locator

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The activities accomplished during the first half of the AD4GD project concerning the WP3 Heterogeneous IoT Data Integration and the application of standard protocols. A list of requirements for IoT gathered in collaboration with the three pilots created in the AD4GD project is presented. Different sources of IoT data that match the needs of the pilots were identified such as water quality sensors, camera traps and air quality sensors. The aspects linked to the IoT were considered in the proposed architecture for the intended Green Deal Data Space. Several components related to IoT data management are included in the GDDS architecture, such as an NGINX proxy server, a FROST-OGC SensorThings API server, FIWARE context brokers, and a TM Forum IoT server. The APIs and the corresponding data models are presented in this report for each service installed in the IoT Lab research infrastructure. We have demonstrated that a mapping between different data models is possible and facilitates the interoperability and the integration of the heterogeneous sources of IoT data. Some tools are developed to push data generated by IoT sensors deployed in a small lake in the Berlin region, for the extraction of GBIF data and for importing Air quality data. The use of edge computing next to the IoT sensor is compared with the implementation of IoT and HPC.

Based on the project review report this deliverable was augmented with a description of the Simpl initiative development and the risks concerning delays or failure to deliver the components and open source promised by the Simpl initiative. Currently the Simpl deliverables are still immature and there is a high probability that AD4GD project will finalize before stable SIMPL components have been released. However this should not impact on the project executions because the current architecture proposed by the DSSC allows for the replacement of components that use the similar standards. Additional information related to the Internet of Things in all the three pilots covered by the AD4GD project was added: For the the pilot 2, the description and the use of the camera traps in biodiversity are explained and the IoT air quality sensors for pilot 3 were added.

1 INTRODUCTION

The WP3 task “Heterogeneous IoT Data Integration” is in charge of the data integration in the Green Deal Data Space (GDDS) together with the WP2 “In situ networks, CitSci and Socioeconomic Data” and WP4 “Satellite and Green Data Space Integration,” but with specific focus on Internet of Things (IoT) data. The WP3 objectives are the definition of the technical specification for integrating heterogeneous IoT data, the tools parsing the heterogeneous IoT data based on this specification and optimizing data processing at the edge.

The main tool to be developed in the WP3 is the multi-protocol proxy as a service used between the data sources and the Green Deal Data Space. It will facilitate the integration of the heterogeneous data in the AD4GD dataspace. This tool will support different communication protocols based on the technical specifications defined in this document.

1.1 PURPOSE OF THE DELIVERABLE

This deliverable reports the work done in Task T3.1 “Heterogeneous IoT data integration model” (M1-M33), Task T3.2 “IoT multi-protocol parser as a service” (M1-M33) and the Task T3.3 “Scalability and edge computing optimization” (M13-M33).

Task T3.1 defines the technical integration model of heterogeneous IoT data, notably through open APIs and data modeling. The activities done in this task are based on the requirements and the architecture provided by the other WPs. The task follows an iterative process to consider all developments made in the AD4GD project.

Task T3.2 is the concrete development of the heterogeneous IoT data integration into its implementation corresponding to the IoT multi-protocol parser as a service. It aims to support different communication and application protocols based on the IoT devices to be deployed in the context of the AD4GD dataspace.

Finally, Task T3.3 handles the scalability and the optimization at the edge computing level. Concretely, this task is defining several KPIs that measure the performance and the scalability at the edge in the dedicated optimization process.

2 METHODOLOGY

The methodology applied in the WP3 is to collect the latest information available in the state of the art concerning the integration of IoT into a data space. Different sources are used at the European level, notably the experiences gained in previous European projects or initiatives. Furthermore, an iterative process was put in place since the beginning of the project to discuss and share the requirements and the architecture of the Green Deal Data Space with all partners and other stakeholders. The discussions related to the Internet of Things are centralised into a GitLab server put in place by IoT Lab for internal use in the AD4GD project; these discussions are represented by GitLab issues tagged with the word “IoT.” This allows an iterative and constructive approach guiding the development of WP3.

3 IoT AND DATASPACE

In the Internet of Things (IoT) perspective, a data space comprises three parts: IoT devices, edge computing, and cloud computing. An IoT device can be a sensor, an actuator, or an appliance communicating on the Internet. Edge computing offers data storage and computation capabilities closer to data generation. Cloud computing represents the data storage and the computation features available at large scale in data centres. The combination of IoT devices, edge computing, and cloud computing is called computing continuum and ensures data transmission from the source, the IoT devices, to the consumers in the cloud. It is important to guarantee the computing continuum in a data space containing IoT data. The data generated by the heterogeneous IoT devices should be accessible to data consumers depending on the data usage guidelines defined in a data space.

Of course, several requirements should be defined to ensure the availability of heterogeneous IoT data. The AD4GD deliverable D1.1 “Multi-actor and knowledge centres co-design and requirements definition report (draft),” provides an initial list of requirements in section 8. All the requirements were analysed from the point of view of IoT: it means that the IoT part of the Green Deal Data Space should consider and fulfil the relevant requirements.

The search feature is the first requirement for the Green Deal Data Space (GDDS). Users should be able to retrieve datasets based on a location or region. Concretely, it means that IoT data contains information about the location. In other words, the data generated by IoT devices should encompass the localisation, or a way to add the localisation to the IoT data should be provided.

The second requirement concerns semantic interoperability: the datasets should be grouped by topics, and the IoT data should follow the topics defined in the context of the GDDS.

The presence of metadata is the third requirement, and thus, the IoT data should contain the related metadata by default, or there is a manner to add the metadata to the IoT datasets to be registered into the GDDS. The metadata should encompass the author, the date of the last modification, the temporal coverage, and the licence. Further metadata can be the information related to the data quality and the method used for the IoT data collection.

The fourth requirement states that the GDDS should include as many providers as possible. This includes, of course, the sources of heterogeneous IoT data.

The fifth requirement is the implementation of basic data transformation, typically the conversion of units and timestamps. Some of these proposed conversions could already be done in the IoT components during the IoT data collection.

The last requirement enforces the data access control system. This mechanism defines how to access the data, including the heterogeneous IoT data. It is particularly useful when data sharing is restricted to some users with specific conditions. By default, the IoT data is expected to be published in an open access. However, several use cases limit data access. The WP3 is also following the principles of security and privacy by design.

Of course, new requirements can be added to the AD4GD project based on the needs and requirements expressed by the three pilots. In this case, they will be examined, and solutions related to the Internet of Things will be developed.

4 IoT DATA SOURCES

The initial heterogeneous IoT data sources were chosen following the needs of the pilots in the first stage of the AD4GD project, notably during the pilot kick-off meeting organised in Bonn in September 2023.

4.1 PILOT 1 (WATER QUANTITY AND QUALITY)

Concerning the first pilot dedicated to the monitoring of the lakes in the Berlin region, the Internet of Things can facilitate the automated collection of data related to the water quality and water availability of different lakes. It is important for the local authorities to know the current state of each monitored lake and the long-term trend of the different properties measured by the sensors placed in the lakes. It also means to store the historical data about the water quality. The environmental variables measured in the small lakes around Berlin were defined in the pilot kick-off meeting and encompass the water level, the water temperature, and the oxygen. These different kinds of data are available on the Wasserportal of Berlin¹ as CSV or XML files.

4.2 PILOT 2 (BIODIVERSITY)

The second pilot concerns the region of Catalonia and calculates the terrestrial connectivity of the different habitats for 7 quinquennial periods: 1987, 1992, 1997, 2002, 2007, 2012, 2017 and 2022. The maps need to be enriched by the species' data generated by direct Citizen Science observations and by the IoT sensors. IoT sensors are available such as camera traps and radio tracking devices. The measurements permit the determination of the position of wild animals. In the case of the pilot 2 in AD4GD, only camera traps are used. These camera traps are positioned in places that have been diagnosed as "corridors", which are critical narrow paths connecting patches of the same habitat type. Camera traps sensors can help to demonstrate that corridors are effective and used by animals, in particular those of protected endangered species, that are considered sensitive by this pilot.

For this study, three cameras have been acquired, of two different models. The first model consists of a Browning Trail Camera Dark Ops Pro X 1080 (two cameras acquired) which is designed for wildlife monitoring and research, and the second model consists of a Sentinel II 940 NM SCOUT GUARD (Figure 1). Both models work with infrared flash using "black" LEDs, also known as "no-glow" LED's, which emit energy in the infrared range. This technique is used in trail cameras to capture images and videos and low-light or night-time condition without emitting visible light. Black LEDs provide sufficient illumination for the camera's sensor to capture clear images in complete darkness or in poor light conditions. This technology provides key benefits when monitoring wildlife such as causing minimal disturbance to animals and

¹ <https://wasserportal.berlin.de/start.php>

fewer attacks on the equipment by potential intruders. Key specifications of each camera can be visualised in table 1.

Figure 1: Browning Trail Camera Dark Ops Pro X 1080 Model (on the left) and STRIKE FORCE PRO X 1080 Model (on the right)

Brand & Model	Capture Mode	Infrared LED	Infrared LED wavelength	Sensor Resolution (MP)	Field of View	Image Detection Angle	Image Detection Range	Video Resolution	Memory Card type	Memory card Capacity (GB)	Batteries AA	Trigger Speed	Multishot	Screen
Browning DARK OPS PRO X 1080	Photo/Video/Photo Video	black	940 nm	4, 8, 12 or 24	55°	45°	30.5 m	Full HD 1080p Videos with Sound	SD	512	6	0.22 s	1 up to 8 images	viewing screen for settings programming, photo/video viewing and camera placement and focusing
SENTINEL II 940 NM SCOUT GUARD	Photo/Video/Photo Video	black	940 nm	1, 3, 5, 8, 12, 16 or 20	80°	90°	25 m	Full HD 1080p Videos with Sound	SD	32	8	0.4 s	1, 2 or 3 images	viewing screen for settings programming, photo/video viewing and camera placement and focusing

Table 1: Main characteristics of the cameras acquired.

These cameras have been deployed in the north-east of Catalonia in the Albera Natural Park where still some individuals of the endangered species *Mustela putorius* are known to exist. Also in the Albera Natural Park inhabits the *Felis silvestris* protected species. These two species are the ones to be monitored within the pilot. The cameras have been installed in two main animal corridors (Figure 2) which were known and proposed by the Natural Park technicians.

Figure 2: Cameras deployed in Albera Natural Park corridors

Once the images have been captured, these need to be analysed in terms of species recognition (Figure 3 and 4).

Figure 3: Image acquired by the Browning Trail Camera Dark Ops Pro X 1080 camera

Figure 4: Image acquired by the STRIKE FORCE PRO X 1080 camera

After species recognition is done, data will be uploaded into the FROST server via STApplus taking into account sensitive privacy data issues in terms of species and camera location.

4.3 PILOT 3 (AIR QUALITY)

This pilot study investigates the potential of using data from IoT/low-cost sensors to predict air quality and explores whether this data provides additional benefits for air pollution forecasting systems.

To achieve this, we first assessed the available sensor measurement networks to determine their suitability for our investigations. Two measurement networks stood out in particular: Sensor.Community and PurpleAir.

Sensor.Community is a citizen science project where individuals purchase air quality sensors and install them in their homes. The data collected is then made freely available to everyone via the platform's website (<https://sensor.community>) and an API. PurpleAir operates on a similar model, though it is a paid service. However, until March 2024, all PurpleAir measurements were freely accessible through the OpenAQ portal (<https://openaq.org/>).

Both networks primarily focus on monitoring particulate matter concentrations (specifically PM10 and PM2.5, i.e. particles with an aerodynamic diameter less than 10 and 2.5 micrometres, respectively). These concentrations are measured using a nephelometric method and the data is made available almost instantaneously via the API. The IoT measurements include of course, the location and the timestamp. The type of sensor is also included, otherwise it is added in the metadata.

Figure 5 below illustrates the geographical distribution of both sensor networks across Europe, showing very good coverage in Central, Eastern, and South-Eastern Europe.

Figure 5: Distribution of IoT sensors across Europe.

Despite these promising conditions, the data comes with some limitations. Besides the massive data volume of several hundred gigabytes, the measurements are subject to certain errors. The raw data from IoT sensors exhibits high variability and noise, necessitating statistical methods for signal smoothing. Additionally, the measurement time series often contain outliers, requiring standardization and outlier filtering.

A major challenge is the limited availability of representative reference measurements for a field of air pollutants, which come with pronounced spatial-temporal gradients. Standardization can be achieved through simple statistical methods tailored to individual stations. For outlier detection and filtering, using other (reliable) observations is a practical strategy. Employing various AI/ML tools could also be an effective approach.

Ultimately, using the cleaned measurement time series with established geostatistical methods (Ordinary Kriging or Innovation Kriging), it might be possible to provide retrospective maps of air pollutants and relevant indicators with high temporal and spatial resolution. Due to the almost instantaneous availability of the measurement data, it might also become feasible to create near-real-time maps of various air quality parameters.

An example of using particulate matter measurements from IoT data is given in Figure 6 for the city of Sofia. Sofia is particularly prone to air pollution due to its geographical location in a valley

surrounded by mountains, which can trap pollutants. Additionally, heavy traffic emissions from older vehicles and the widespread use of solid fuels for domestic heating exacerbate the problem.

However, the city also benefits from hundreds of low-cost sensors from Sensor.Community placed throughout the area. The data collected by these sensors enable us to create high-resolution maps of pollution levels, such as PM2.5, allowing us to clearly identify different pollution hotspots within the Sofia area.

Figure 6: Distribution of IoT stations in Sofia (left) and regridded PM2.5 concentration on 250x250m² resolution (right). Colorshading indicates monthly mean PM2.5 concentration for December 2022.

5 ARCHITECTURE

The architecture of the IoT part composing the Green Deal Data Space is presented in this section. This architecture was elaborated in collaboration with the other partners involved in the technical Work Packages of the AD4GD project. Figure 7 presents the high-level view of the current architecture developed for the AD4GD Green Deal Data Space:

Figure 7: High-level view of AD4GD Green Deal Data Space architecture.

In Figure 7, the IoT sensors are deployed in the three pilots for the specific use cases. Before collecting the data generated by the IoT sensors, each pilot determined if the different types of data were sensitive. If the pilot considers that there is no privacy and data protection risk, the data can be published as open data. On the other hand, when the pilot considers the data as sensitive, the AD4GD architecture permits the use of the data space connector concept. This concept implements contracts between parties for the protection of sensitive data sharing, notably by implementing data authentication, access policies, and licences. Independently of the sensitivity of the data, dedicated processes are made on the IoT data to make them interoperable. These processes encompass the use of the common vocabularies, the application of the data models (i.e., the AD4GD information model developed in WP1), and the generation of the related metadata. Ultimately, the IoT data is converted to the JSON format used by the OGC SensorThings API and sent to the FROST server hosted and managed by IoT Lab.

The storage of the IoT data in the FROST server, which implements the OGC SensorThings API, allows the retrieval of the data generated by the sensors through time series in a standard way. It also means that the stored data are accessible independently of the availability of the sensors in the network.

6 COMPONENTS

This section presents the different components to manage the heterogeneous IoT data.

6.1 NGINX

An NGINX server was installed as a reverse proxy server. It permits increased security and data protection, complying with the principle of security and privacy by design. It handles the TLS encryption for the HTTPS protocol and the related Let's Encrypt certificates. It also assumes the role of load balancer for the servers hidden behind it. Figure 8 shows the NGINX server in front of the diverse components used for the IoT data:

Figure 8: NGINX server with IoT components.

The NGINX server is used to protect the other servers deployed to store and manage IoT data. The NGINX server redirects the requests to the right component depending on the URL of the request and the TCP port. Each server dedicated to IoT data is presented in the next sections.

Three different servers are available behind the NGINX proxy server. These three servers allow the users to reach out to different IoT devices and their data using different IoT communication protocols. It is designed to provide different ways to access information depending on the IoT protocols supported by the IoT devices. If an IoT device supports several IoT communication protocols, the users have the choice to access the information by the different protocols. In this case, an IoT device is connected to the different servers.

6.2 FROST SERVER

A FROST server was deployed and configured in the IoT Lab research infrastructure. This server implements the OGC SensorThings API presented in the next chapter. Furthermore, a specific plugin named “SensorThings API -PLUS” (STApplus) was also installed within the FROST server. The objective of the plugin is to ease the implementation of the FAIR principles in the FROST server.

The FROST server is following the OGC SensorThings API specified in the official account of OGC². The FROST server is composed of two main endpoints: <https://frost.iotlab.com/sensorthingsapi/> and <https://frost.iotlab.com/sensorthings/>. The first one corresponds to the URL <http://frost.iotlab.com:8090/FROST-Server/v1.1> and it is in fact the OGC SensorThings API ready to use for any Sensor Things API compatible software client. The second endpoint represents the URL <http://frost.iotlab.com:8090/FROST-Server/> and permits a user to test requests to the FROST server directly through a Graphical User Interface (GUI) without the need to use cURL or Postman on his computer. The FROST GUI also contains all the links to the different parts of the FROST server, in function of the configuration.

To dive more into the implementation details, the source code of the FROST server is open source and available on GitHub³ and the programming language is Java. Furthermore, the STApplus plugin for the FROST server is also written in Java and is published as open-source software⁴.

² <https://docs.ogc.org/is/15-078r6/15-078r6.html>

³ <https://github.com/FraunhoferIOSB/FROST-Server>

⁴ <https://github.com/securedimensions/FROST-Server-PLUS>

Figure 9: FROST server architecture (source: <https://fraunhoferiosb.github.io/FROST-Server/deployment/architecture-packages.html>).

Figure 9 presents the architecture of the FROST server as installed in the IoT Lab research infrastructure. The data generated by the sensors can be sent using one of the two possible communication protocols: HTTP or MQTT. Of course, the implementation of the FROST server supports the CRUD operations, namely creation, reading, update, and deletion of the data in the database of the FROST server. These operations are undertaken through the endpoints provided by the OGC SensorThings API.

6.3 FIWARE CONTEXT BROKERS

To complete the FROST server, FIWARE components were installed in order to support the interoperability and integration with data sources compatible with the protocols supported natively by FIWARE. The protocols are NGSI-LD (Next Generation Service Interfaces Linked Data) and NGSIv2 (Next Generation Service Interfaces version 2); they represent the most used protocols for open-source platforms dedicated to IoT in Europe and beyond. For each protocol, a specific FIWARE context broker is available. For the most recent protocol, namely NGSI-LD, the URL of the context broker, named Orion-LD, is <https://frost.iotlab.com/ngsild/>. On the other hand, the FIWARE context broker for NGSIv2, simply named Orion, is reachable at <https://frost.iotlab.com/ngsiv2/>. Both FIWARE context brokers are written in C++ and are open

source and freely available on GitHub⁵for the NGSI-LD protocol (Orion-LD) and for the NGSIv2 protocol (Orion)⁶.

Figure 10 displays the components used for a typical FIWARE deployment:

Figure 10: FIWARE components (source: <https://github.com/FIWARE/catalogue>).

As shown in Figure 10, the FIWARE context broker plays the major role in a standard FIWARE deployment. It receives the data coming from the underlying IoT devices. From the context broker, the data is distributed to other databases for long storage and for specific data processing. Finally, the data can be visualised through different kinds of dashboards or tools.

The FIWARE community provides IoT devices and related software components using the two NGSI-LD and NGSIv2 data formats. These IoT devices can be good candidates to be deployed in the pilots in function of the needs and requirements elaborated by the AD4GD pilots. The dedicated section of the FIWARE marketplace is located at <https://www.fiware.org/marketplace/fiware-ready/>.

6.4 TM FORUM IoT SERVER

A server implementing the IoT APIs developed for TM Forum was installed. It can be used to collect data from potential IoT devices compatible with the TM Forum IoT APIs described in the dedicated section below. The TMF908 IoT Agent and Device Management API is one of the 70 Open APIs developed and published by TM Forum. The industry widely uses these Open APIs. The current statistics given by TM Forum encompass 640.000 downloads by 39.000 software

⁵ <https://github.com/FIWARE/context.Orion-LD>

⁶ <https://github.com/telefonicaid/fiware-orion>

developers working in 2.500 organisations. Therefore, it makes sense to take into consideration the TMF908 API offered by the TM Forum IoT server⁷ hosted by IoT Lab. The corresponding URL is frost.iotlab.com/tmforum/. The specification of the APIs is directly available on the server⁸. These APIs are using the principles of OpenAPI specification, previously known as Swagger specification. Through the specification, it is possible to automatically generate the skeleton of the IoT APIs, notably by employing the Swagger Editor⁹. In our case, the server was generated in Java. Figure 11 presents the different endpoints of the IoT Agent and Device API specified by TM Forum:

The screenshot shows the Swagger UI interface for the IoT Agent and Device API. The main heading is "Agent and Device" with the subtitle "My api short documentation". Below this, there is a list of API endpoints, each with a "Show/Hide", "List Operations", and "Expand Operations" link. The endpoints listed are: alarm, dataAccessEndpoint, events subscription, iotDataEvent, iotDevice, iotDeviceSpecification, iotManagementEvent, notification listeners (client side), and resourceSpecification. At the bottom of the page, it indicates the base URL as "/" and the API version as "4.0.0".

Figure 11: Specification and documentation of the IoT APIs

More information on IoT APIs can be found in the following section.

7 APIs

The APIs dedicated to the Internet of Things are numerous. So, a selection has been made in the project, taking into account the needs and requirements discovered previously for the GDSS.

7.1 OGC SENSORTHINGS API

The OGC SensorThings API is an open standard specifying an API dedicated to the Internet of Things. It is based on the Representational State Transfer (REST) principles and the OASIS Open

⁷ <https://frost.iotlab.com/tmforum>

⁸ <https://frost.iotlab.com/tmforum/swagger-ui.html>

⁹ <https://editor.swagger.io/>

Data Protocol (OData) corresponding to the ISO/IEC 20802 standard. The OGC SensorThings API is built on top of the HTTP and MQTT application layer protocols. MQTT (MQ Telemetry Transport) was originally developed by IBM to monitor oil pipelines via satellites, but now it is well used in the context of IoT transmissions.

The standard defining the OGC SensorThings API is composed of two parts:

- SensorThings API Part 1¹⁰: It is named “Sensing” and permits retrieval and management of the observations and the metadata provided by the IoT sensors.
- SensorThings API Part 2¹¹: Its title is “Tasking Core” and sets the parameters of IoT devices, platforms linked to IoT, mobile devices, etc.

The data model used by the OGC SensorThings API is based on the Observations and Measurements (O&M) standard which corresponds also to the ISO 19156 standard. The Observations and Measurements standard is one of the core standards of OGC Sensor Web Enablement (SWE).

Figure 12 is a schema representing the data model of the OGC SensorThings API:

Figure 12: OGC SensorThings API data model

¹⁰ <https://docs.ogc.org/is/15-078r6/15-078r6.html>

¹¹ <https://docs.ogc.org/is/17-079r1/17-079r1.html>

The different components of the OGC SensorThings API data model are described as follows:

- **Datastream**: a collection of observations made by an IoT sensor.
- **FeatureOfInterest**: a property of an observation. For example, the location of an IoT sensor.
- **HistoricalLocation**: the history of the last known and previous locations of a thing.
- **Location**: the location of a thing.
- **Observation**: a measurement.
- **ObservedProperty**: name, definition and description of a measurement. For instance, the wind velocity and direction.
- **Sensor**: the physical sensor.
- **Thing**: a physical or virtual object.

An extension named “STApplus”¹² has been added to the Sensor Things API server and extends the OGC SensorThings API data model. The aim of this module is to make the data stored by a Sensor Things API server FAIR. This is achieved by using licenses and ownership information.

This extension adds the following entities to the OGC SensorThings API data model:

- **Party**: an acting user who can authenticate to the Sensor Things API server.
- **PartyRoleCode**: the code attributed to the role of a party.
- **License**: a license associated with a Datastream or to a MultiDatastream, to a Campaign, and to an ObservationGroup.
- **Campaign**: a period of measurements linked to a privacy policy and terms of use.
- **ObservationGroup**: a group containing several Observations.
- **Relation**: a relationship between an Observation and an ObservationGroup.

The main difficulty in applying the data model to IoT is the realisation of the separation of concerns and the need to adapt the generic model to the needs of specific domains. Commonly every variable is encoded as an independent observation that is part of a datastream that is associated to a unit of measure and to an observedProperty definition.

¹² <https://docs.ogc.org/is/22-022r1/22-022r1.html>


```

▼ value:
  ▼ 0:
    ▶ @iot.selfLink: "https://citiobs.demo.sec...1.1/Observations(126026)"
    @iot.id: 126026
    phenomenonTime: "2023-07-26T16:15:15Z"
    result: "25.92"
    resultTime: "2023-07-26T16:15:15Z"
    ▼ Datastream:
      name: "Air Temperature"
      ▼ unitOfMeasurement:
        name: "Celsius"
        symbol: "C"
        definition: "https://qudt.org/vocab/unit/DEG_C"
      ▼ ObservedProperty:
        ▶ @iot.selfLink: "https://citiobs.demo.sec...1/ObservedProperties(17)"
        @iot.id: 17
        definition: "http://vocabs.lter-europe.net/EnvThes/22035"
        description: "Air Temperature"
        name: "temp"

```

Figure 13: OGC Basic representation of Sensor Things API data model dedicated to weather data¹³.

7.2 FIWARE

FIWARE is an open-source framework allowing the creation of interoperable IoT platforms. The main domains, also called verticals, are Smart AgriFood, Smart Cities, Smart Energy, Smart Industry, and Smart Water. Currently, FIWARE is using two open standards for its API:

- NGSI-v2 (Next Generation Service Interfaces version 2)
- NGSI-LD (Next Generation Service Interfaces Linked Data)

NGSI-LD is the current version which is standardised by ETSI ISG CIM (European Telecommunications Standardization Institute Industry Specification Group cross-cutting Context Information Management). NGSI-LD is using a metamodel partially based on JSON-LD (JavaScript Object Notation-Linked Data). Five key concepts are utilised by the FIWARE NGSI-API:

- Entity: a representation of a real object.
- Property: an attribute of an entity.
- Relationship: link based on the five concepts.
- Type: a Web Ontology Language (OWL) class. It can also be defined by the users.
- Value: JSON or JSON-LD value.

¹³ [https://citiobs.demo.secure-dimensions.de/staplus/v1.1/Datastreams\(17\)/Observations?\\$expand=Datastream\(\\$select=name,unitOfMeasurement;\\$expand=ObservedProperty\)](https://citiobs.demo.secure-dimensions.de/staplus/v1.1/Datastreams(17)/Observations?$expand=Datastream($select=name,unitOfMeasurement;$expand=ObservedProperty))

The FIWARE community is also specifying and using smart data models which are publicly available¹⁴. There are two types of smart data model representations:

- Basic representation
- Normalised representation

Figure 14 shows an example of basic representation of a smart data model dedicated to water quality:

```
1  {
2    "id": "urn:ngsi-ld:WaterQualityObserved:waterqualityobserved:Sevilla:D1",
3    "type": "WaterQualityObserved",
4    "NO3": 0.01,
5    "conductivity": 0.005,
6    "dateObserved": "2017-01-31T06:45:00Z",
7    "location": {
8      "coordinates": [
9        -5.993307,
10       37.362882
11      ],
12      "type": "Point"
13    },
14    "measurand": [
15      "NO3, 0.01, M1, Concentration of Nitrates"
16    ],
17    "pH": 7.4,
18    "temperature": 24.4,
19    "flow": 127.53,
20    "@context": [
21      "https://uri.etsi.org/ngsi-ld/v1/ngsi-ld-core-context.jsonld",
22      "https://raw.githubusercontent.com/smart-data-models/dataModel.WaterQuality/master/context.jsonld"
23    ]
24  }
```

Figure 14: OGC Basic representation of a smart data model dedicated to water quality.

Figure 15 below displays an example of a smart data model using the normalised representation:

¹⁴ <https://smartdatamodels.org/>


```
1 {
2   "id": "urn:ngsi-ld:WaterQualityObserved:waterqualityobserved:Sevilla:D1",
3   "type": "WaterQualityObserved",
4   "NO3": {
5     "type": "Property",
6     "value": 0.01
7   },
8   "conductivity": {
9     "type": "Property",
10    "value": 0.005
11  },
12  "dateObserved": {
13    "type": "Property",
14    "value": {
15      "@type": "DateTime",
16      "@value": "2017-01-31T06:45:00Z"
17    }
18  },
19  "location": {
20    "type": "GeoProperty",
21    "value": {
22      "type": "Point",
23      "coordinates": [
24        -5.993307,
25        37.362882
26      ]
27    }
28  },
29 }
```

Figure 15: Normalised representation of a smart data model dedicated to water quality.

7.3 TM FORUM IoT APIS

TM Forum is a global industry association regrouping more than 850 members, including telephone companies, cable and network operators, cloud providers, hardware and software suppliers, and communications service providers (CSPs). TM Forum aims to ease the digital transformation in the telecommunications industry. One of the main initiatives in this area is the TM Forum Open APIs.

These Open APIs allow connectivity between multiple partners, interoperability, and portability across the available services. Furthermore, they enable good management of heterogeneous services. The basic application domain of the TM Forum Open APIs is the OSS (Operations Support Systems) and the BSS (Business Support Systems), both located at the core of the telecommunications providers. The TM Forum community developed around 60 REST Open APIs, which are largely used worldwide.

In the context of IoT, TM Forum has designed and implemented two TM Forum IoT APIs:

- TMF908 IoT Agent and Device API Component Suite.
- TMF914 IoT Service Management API Component Suite.

The specifications of these Open APIs dedicated to IoT are based on polymorphism and extension patterns. The TM Forum community defines the related data models, but they are aligned with FIWARE NGSI concerning the attributes. The payloads of the TM Forum Open APIs are in JSON. Swagger tools generate the source code of these Open APIs.

The TMF908 IoT Agent and Device API manages IoT devices and agents. An agent can be considered an IoT gateway for a group of IoT devices. This API allows the collection of data generated by IoT devices, the actuation of IoT devices when possible, the configuration of IoT devices, and finally, the monitoring of IoT devices, including alarms. The TMF908 IoT Agent and Device API is a data model that comprises 103 entities and 22 endpoints.

Figure 16 is an example showing the payload of DataAccessEndpoint resource object defined in the TMF908 IoT Agent and Device API:

```
{
  "category": "Gold",
  "description": "This is a temperature sensor using CoAP and 6LoWPAN.",
  "endDate": "2019-05-13T00:00",
  "href": "https://host:port/tmf-api/iotDevice/v1/iotDevice/temp_3",
  "id": "3",
  "lifecycleState": "InService",
  "name": "temp_3",
  "startDate": "2019-05-03T00:00",
  "value": "0041227744222",
  "version": "1.0",
  "apiType": "NGSI",
  "uri": "https://host:port/tmf-api/iotDevice/v1/iotDevice/temp_3/dataAccessEndpoint/3"
}
```

Figure 16: Example of payload used by the TMF908 API.

The TMF914 IoT Service Management API is providing a service fully dedicated to IoT. This IoT service can manage all the IoT devices with other TM Forum services. The basic principle of a TM Forum service is to increase interoperability and scalability. Furthermore, the IoT service permits the monetization of the data coming from the IoT devices, particularly the sensors. The data model specified for the TMF914 IoT Service Management API encompasses 196 entities and 36 endpoints.

Figure 17 shows a typical example of a payload used by the TMF914 IoT Service Management API when a ServiceCategory resource object is transmitted through this API:


```

{
  "href": "https://iotlab.com/tmf-api/iot servicemanagement/v4/serviceCategory/1700",
  "id": "1700",
  "category": [
    {
      "id": "5980",
      "href": "https://iotlab.com/tmf-api/iot servicemanagement/v4/serviceCategory/5980",
      "version": "1.0",
      "name": "Universal Device Gateway",
      "@referredType": "ServiceCategory",
      "@type": "ServiceCategoryRef",
      "@schemaLocation": "https://iotlab.com/tmf-api/schema/Service/ServiceCategoryRef.schema.json",
      "@baseType": ""
    }
  ],
  "description": "A category to hold all available IoT platforms.",
  "isRoot": false,
  "lastUpdate": "2020-09-03T00:00:00.00Z",
  "lifecycleStatus": "Active",
  "name": "IoT Platform Services",
  "parentId": "104",
  "validFor": {
    "startDateTime": "2017-08-24T00:00:00.00Z",
    "endDateTime": "2021-03-25T00:00:00.00Z"
  },
  "version": "1.0"
}

```

Figure 17: Example of a payload used by the TMF914 API.

7.4 CAMTRAP DP DATA MODEL

Camera Trap Data Package (Camtrap DP) is a community-developed standard that allows users to easily exchange, harmonise and store camera trap data and metadata of camera trap studies. This standard has been built upon the Camera Trap Metadata Standard¹⁵ (CTMS) and developed under the umbrella of the Biodiversity Information Standards¹⁶ (TDWG). Camtrap DP is based on the so-called Frictionless Standards¹⁷, a set of generic specifications to describe and to package tabular data and metadata, expressed as Javascript Object Notation format. Camtrap DP is specifically built upon the Frictionless Data Package, being the latter a simple container format used to describe and package a collection of data.

Camtrap DP is a data package consisting of four files (see Figure 18). First, the standard defines a profile to capture the essential metadata of the data package and the camera trap project as datapackage.json which is based on the Frictionless Data Package.

Second, the standard specifies 3 resources to capture the data collected by the project: the “deployments.csv” resource, which details the camera trap placements; the “media.csv” resource, which contains the media files recorded during the camera trap deployments; and the “observations.csv” resource, which includes the observations identified in the media files. These resources are tabular data stored in CSV files that can be described with the Tabular data resource Standard (<https://specs.frictionlessdata.io/tabular-data-resource/>).

File	Description
------	-------------

¹⁵ <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC526752>

¹⁶ <https://www.tdwg.org>

¹⁷ <https://frictionlessdata.io>

datapackage.json	Metadata about the data package and camera trap project.
deployments.csv	Table with camera trap placements (deployments).
media.csv	Table with media files recorded during deployments.
observations.csv	Table with observations derived from the media files.

Figure 18: Camtrap DP files and files descriptions.

All these elements collectively represent a data model for exchanging camera trap data. In Figure 19, a schema representing the structure of a Camtrap DP can be observed. It encompasses the metadata file (datapackage.json) and the three above described resources as tabular data files (deployments.csv, media.csv, observations.csv). The resources are interrelated through foreign keys. For example, deployments.csv is linked to media.csv via the *deploymentID* field, media.csv is connected to observations.csv through the *mediaID* field, and observations.csv is related to deployments.csv by the *deploymentsID* field.

Figure 19: Schema representing the structure of Camtrap DP data model.

Overall, Camera Trap Data Package is a simple and yet flexible data model for defining structured metadata for images, sequences, and events, thus facilitating data sharing and reuse across different camera trap platforms and studies.

8 IoT DATA MODELS

This section explains the models of the IoT data mentioned in the previous sections of this document and how they affect the IoT part of the Green Deal Data Space. The goal is to try to map the different APIs into a common IoT data model, allowing the exchange of information from the heterogeneous IoT sensors encountered in the Green Deal Data Space.

In the context of the AD4GD project, the OGC STA data model is the basis of the work concerning IoT data. This API is the cornerstone to collect and unify the data generated by the heterogeneous IoT devices required to implement the three pilots. As mentioned earlier, 8 attributes from the OGC STA data models are taken into consideration: Datastream, FeatureOfInterest, HistoricalLocation, Location, Observation, ObservedProperty, Sensor, and finally, Thing.

For the FIWARE NGSI-LD and NGSI v2 APIs, which are running on smart platforms for IoT, the data model Device (<https://github.com/smart-data-models/dataModel.Device/tree/15b7f2705238e8a9028807eed8f05b15d7892569/Device>) is used to represent an IoT device. The FIWARE community considers that an IoT device comprises hardware, software, and firmware and can sense the environment or do some actions. A Device has several attributes employed to convey measurements, metadata, and other information concerning an IoT device.

Finally, the specification of the TM Forum TMF908 IoT Agent and Device Component Suite API (<https://www.tmforum.org/resources/specification/tmf908-iot-agent-and-device-component-suite-api-specification-v1-0/>) is using an entity named `iotDevice` which represents an IoT device. The corresponding data model permits the configuration and management of each IoT device. At the same time, the data generated by such IoT devices can be retrieved based on the data model implemented through the TMF908 API.

8.1 STAPLUS AND FIWARE NGSI-LD, NGSI v2 AND TMF908 API MAPPINGS

Figure 20 shows the mapping between the different IoT communication protocols or standards. The mapping is realised through the entities and attributes used in the respective data model mentioned in this document:

OGC SensorThings API	NGSI-LD / NGSI v2 APIs	TMF908 API
Datastream	Device, in particular: Device.deviceCategory Device.controlledProperty Device.value Device.location	iotDevice, in particular: iotDevice.category iotDevice.characteristic iotDevice.location
FeatureOfInterest	Device.*	iotDevice.*
HistoricalLocation	Device.location	iotDevice.location
Location	Device.location	iotDevice.location
Observation	Device.value	iotDevice.characteristic
ObservedProperty	Device.controlledProperty	iotDevice.characteristic
Sensor	Device.deviceCategory	iotDevice.category
Thing	Device	iotDevice

Figure 20: Mapping of the IoT data models: OGC SensorThingAPI, FIWARE NGSI-LD/NGSI v2, and TMF908 API.

The main principle applied for mapping IoT data is to link the attributes and properties from IoT protocols and standards with the OGC SensorThings API. The OGC SensorThings API is the central API used for IoT data in the AD4GD Green Deal Data Space context. To realise it, the mapping uses the OGC SensorThings API data model as a reference. It concretely means that the attributes and values from other IoT protocols are mapped to those specified by the data model issued from the OGC SensorThings API.

First, the data model implemented in the OGC SensorThings API uses the notion of “Thing” to represent a real IoT device. This corresponds to “Device” for the FIWARE NGSI-LD and NGSI v2 protocols and “iotDevice” for the TMF908 API.

The notion of “Sensor” encountered in the OGC SensorThings API describes the sensor installed in an IoT device. The correspondence in the FIWARE NGSI-LD and NGSI v2 APIs is “Device.deviceCategory” and, respectively, “iotDevice.category” for the TMF908 API; both allow precise information related to a sensor installed in an IoT device.

Concerning the aspect linked to the location of an IoT device, each protocol has the same notion. Indeed, there are “Location” and “HistoricalLocation” for OGC SensorThings API, “Device.location” for NGSI-LD and NGSI v2, and finally, “iotDevice.location” for TMF908 API.

In the OGC SensorThings API data model, a measurement is represented by two properties or attributes: “ObservedProperty” and “Observation”. “ObservedProperty” is the variable to measure, for instance, the water quality or the temperature. “Observation” is the variable’s value, so the measurement’s value. Both can be mapped to the NGSI-LD and NGSI v2 APIs data model for an

IoT device: first of all, “ObservedProperty” corresponds to “Device.controlledProperty”; then, “Observation” is “Device.value”. In the TMF 908 API data model, both “ObservedProperty” and “Observation” are mapped to “iotDevice.characteristic”, which encompasses not only the value of the measurement but also the unit and the variable of the measurement.

“Datastream” specified in the OGC SensorThings API data model corresponds, in fact, to an aggregation of attributes in the two other data models. In detail, a “Datastream” is composed in the NGSI-LD and NGSI v2 data model by a “Device” described by the attributes “Device.deviceCategory”, “Device.controlledProperty”, “Device.value” and “Device.location”. The same “Datastream” encompasses the information provided through the TMF908 API data model by the attributes “iotDevice.category”, “iotDevice.characteristic” and “iotDevice.location” of an “iotDevice” object.

The data model of the OGC SensorThings API defines “FeatureOfInterest,” which can be mapped to any attributes of a “Device” for NGSI-LD and NGSI v2 and of an “iotDevice” for TMF908 API. A “FeatureOfInterest” represents a property or an attribute to be monitored or observed; it is rather generic, meaning that the mapping to other IoT communication protocols is quite simple.

Figure 21 displays the table doing the mapping between the data model extended by the OGC SensorThings API PLUS plugin, the FIWARE NGSI-LD and NGSI v2 and TMF908 API.

OGC SensorThings API Plus	NGSI-LD / NGSI v2 APIs	TMF908 API
Party	Device.owner	iotDevice.relatedParty
PartyRoleCode	Person Organization	iotDevice.partyRole
License	Device.seeAlso DeviceModel.documentation	iotDevice.characteristic
Campaign	DeviceOperation	iotDevice.dataAccessEndpoint
ObservationGroup	Device.value	iotDevice.characteristic
Relation	Device.seeAlso	iotDevice.resourceRelationship

Figure 21: Mapping the data models: OGC SensorThingAPI PLUS, FIWARE NGSI-LD/NGSI v2, and TMF908 API.

The second mapping concerning the data model used by the OGC STApplus extension consists of finding the same or similar entities or attributes in the other types of data models, namely the FIWARE NGSI-LD and NGSI v2 APIs data models and the TMF908 API data model.

First, the “Party” entity in the OGC SensorThings API PLUS corresponds to a “Device.owner” for FIWARE. On the other hand, the mapping of “Party” with the TMF908 API is done with the

attribute “iotDevice.relatedParty” which is universal across the different Open APIs specified by TM Forum.

FIWARE APIs don't have the notion of “PartyRoleCode” directly, but the mapping can be done with the entities “Person” and “Organization” for an individual and an institution, respectively. Concerning the TMF908 API, the entity “PartyRoleCode” is included in the “iotDevice.partyRole” attribute.

The “License” entity is a little more complex to map with the FIWARE NGSI APIs as no direct license attribute is associated with a device. To achieve this, the attribute “Device.seeAlso” can link a license to an IoT device. Another alternative is the NGSI data model named “DeviceModel” which incorporates the attribute “DeviceModel.documentation”; this can be useful if the license is already part of the documentation published for a given IoT device. The attribute “iotDevice.characteristic” can be employed to map the entity “License” in the context of the TMF908 API.

An entity of the type “Campaign” is mappable with “DeviceOperation” in the FIWARE NGSI APIs and with “iotDevice.dataAccessEndpoint” in the TMF908 API. Indeed, a “DeviceOperation” can collect several measurements released by an IoT device. An “iotDevice.dataAccessEndpoint” is an agent and a channel used by the TMF908 API to retrieve data from a given IoT device; information characterising a “Campaign” in the OGC SensorThings API PLUS is also available in a similar way in the “iotDevice.dataAccessEndpoint”, such the start and the end of data collections or measurements.

An “ObservationGroup” can be mapped with a collection of “Device.value” and “iotDevice.characteristic”, respectively for the data models of NGSI APIs and TMF908.

Finally, the entity “Relation” is similar to “Device.seeAlso” which permits creating links in the FIWARE NGSI APIs. The notion of “Relation” is also available in the TMF908 API through the attribute “iotDevice.resourceRelationship”.

8.2 STAPLUS AND CAMTRAPDP DATA MODEL MAPPING

Work has been done on analysing and mapping the Camtrap DP and the STAplus data models to better understand similarities and cross-fertilization possibilities.

In Figure 22, the two data models are illustrated (Camtrap DP on the left and STAplus on the right). Conceptually, Camtrap DP resources (deployments, media and observations) correspond to STAplus entities. Also, the resource fields of Camtrap DP correspond to the properties of STAplus defining each entity.

Figure 22: Diagrams showing mapped data models. Camtrap DP data model illustrated on the left and SensorThings API plus data model depicted on the right.

In Figure 23, metadata and resources of the Camtrap DP standard have been mapped into STApplus entities and properties. In the context of the metadata, the concept of the “datapackage” from Camtrap DP, which contains the metadata of the camera trap project, has been assimilated into the concept of “Campaign” of STApplus. It is important to note, that while STA does not include a “Campaign” media entity, the STApplus has it.

Regarding deployments, the current STA model does not support the complete mapping of Camtrap DP’s Deployments. However, STA version 2 introduces support for deployments. For the current mapping exercise, Camtrap DP Deployments have been mapped to the “Location” entity of STA, as it is the closest equivalent available.

Lastly, the Observations resource in Camtrap DP also maps to “Observations” in STA. It is worth noting that Camtrap DP includes two types of observations: the media itself (e.g., pictures and videos) and the species identification derived from the media. Both types are effectively accommodated within the STA “Observation” entity.

This mapping and integration highlights the flexibility and extensibility of STApplus, enabling a more comprehensive and efficient data exchange between the Camtrap DP and STA models.

Metadata to STAplus			Deployments to STAplus				
METADATA datapackage.json	Camtrap DP	Camtrap DP fields	STAplus entities/properties	DEPLOYMENT deployments.csv	Camtrap DP	Camtrap DP fields	STAplus entities/properties
	resources	n/a	deploymentID		Thing (to be included in v2)		
	profile	n/a	locationID		Location/id		
	name	Campaign/Name	locationName		Location/name		
	id	Campaign/Id	latitude		Location/location/coordinates[1]		
	created	Campaign/creationTime	longitude		Location/location/coordinates[0]		
	title	Campaign/Description	CoordinateUncertainty		n/a		
	contributors	Party/Group	deploymentStart		To be included in v2		
	description	Campaign/Description	deploymentEnd		To be included in v2		
	version	n/a	setupBy		Party/displayName		
	keywords	n/a	cameraID		Sensor		
	image	n/a	cameraModel		Sensor		
	homepage	n/a	CameraDelay		n/a		
	sources	n/a	CameraHeight		n/a		
	licenses	License	cameraDepth		n/a		
	bibliographicCitation	n/a	cameraTilt		n/a		
	project	n/a	cameraHeading		n/a		
	coordinatePrecision	n/a	detectionDistance		n/a		
	spatial	n/a	timestamplssues		n/a		
	start	Campaign/startTime	baitUse		n/a		
	end	Campaign/endTime	featureType		n/a		
taxonomic	n/a	habitat	n/a				
relatedIdentifiers	n/a	deploymentGroups	n/a				
references	n/a	deploymentComments	n/a				
Media to STAplus			Observations to STAplus				
MEDIA media.csv	Camtrap DP	Camtrap DP fields	STAplus entities/properties	OBSERVATIONS observations.csv	Camtrap DP	Camtrap DP fields	STAplus entities
	mediaID	Observation/Id	observationID		Observation		
	deploymentID	Thing (to be included in v2)	deploymentID		Thing		
	captureMethod	ObservedProperty/name	mediaID		Observation		
	timestamp	Observation/phenomenonTime	eventID		n/a		
	filePath	Observation/Result	eventStart		n/a		
	filePublic	n/a	eventEnd		n/a		
	fileName	Observation/Result	observationLevel		n/a		
	fileMediatype	n/a	observationType		ObservedProperty		
	exifData	n/a	cameraSetupType		Thing		
	favorite	n/a	scientificName		Observation/Result		
	mediaComments	n/a	count		n/a		
		lifeStage	n/a				
		sex	n/a				
		behavior	n/a				
		individualID	n/a				
		individualPositionRadius	n/a				
		individualPositionAngle	n/a				
		individualSpeed	n/a				
		bboxX	n/a				
		bboxY	n/a				
		bboxWidth	n/a				
		bboxHeight	n/a				
		classificationMethod	n/a				
		classifiedBy	Party				
		classificationTimestamp	Observation/phenomenonTime				
		classificationProbability	Observation/resultQuality				
		observationTags	n/a				
		observationComments	n/a				

Figure 23: Mapping of Camtrap DP metadata and resources into STAplus entities and properties.

When comparing Camtrap DP and STAplus data model, it can be concluded that first, it is possible to map Camtrap DP into STAplus, meaning that a tool to transform data from one model to the

other could be developed. The second conclusion is that STApplus is a more flexible model compared to Camtrap DP, which tends to be more domain-specific.

Several gaps have been identified in STA and STApplus where many domain-specific properties are absent. Nevertheless, these gaps can be addressed in at least three ways. Firstly, the property of CoordinateUncertainty of the deployments resource cannot be mapped into STApplus nor STA. This raises the question of whether there is the need to consider this issue in the development of the next STA and STApplus new versions. Secondly, domain-specific properties can be stored using the STA/STApplus properties extension point. Finally, habitat characteristics can be described as properties of the location.

Additionally, gaps in the Camtrap DP have been identified, particularly the lack of support for environmental variables such as temperature and pressure. Camtrap DP currently has no way to accommodate these variables. On the contrary, this limitation can be overcome in STA/STApplus, which allow for an unlimited number of Datastreams.

Overall, it can be highlighted that there is potential for improving both models and the possibility for developing tools to enhance their interoperability and functionality.

The results of this analysis have been presented in the 129th OGC member meeting in Montreal last June 18th 2024 at the Citizen Science DWG (https://portal.ogc.org/services/srv_reserve_meeting_timeslot.php?m=95&t=4627&duration=Tue%2C+Jun+18th+1%3A30pm).

Next steps will focus on proposal of a specific data model for AD4GD camera trap experiment in pilot 2, merging STApplus with some elements of Camtrap DP and performing some tests in FROST server.

9 TOOLS FOR AUTOMATED INGESTION OF DATA FROM DIVERSE SENSORS

This section presents the different tools developed and used by Work Package 3 to integrate IoT data into the Green Deal Data Space. The approach was defined in function of the needs and requirements provided by the three pilots.

The AD4GD Hackathon organised in Birmingham in October 2023 permitted testing and validating the processes and the tools needed to push the IoT data into an instantiation of a FROST server hosted and managed by the IoT Lab team. The data exploited during the Hackathon was provided by the pilot in Berlin and is composed of CSV files. The first dataset from the Berlin pilot consists of a CSV file containing the water height in cm for the Plötzensee, a lake located northwest of Berlin. A second dataset provided by the authorities from Berlin is composed of the measurements associated with the river Spree, which crosses the centre of Berlin. Basically, this dataset contains the water temperature [°C], the specific conductivity [uS/cm], and the number of suspended solids calculated from the value of the conductivity [ppt].

From the two datasets, a common process was created to create the metadata¹⁸ linked to each dataset. Indeed, a JSON file for each received dataset was created to contain the metadata aligned to the outcomes of the different tasks of the project dedicated to the semantic interoperability, and the related vocabularies and ontologies. For the first dataset containing the water level of the Plötzensee, the following JSON file was generated and includes all the required metadata:

1. name: Wasserportal Berlin - Water Level - Ploetzensee
2. description: Water level from Wasserportal Berlin at Ploetzensee
3. locations:
 - a. name: Station number: 5800312, Station name: Ploetzensee, Surface water: Ploetzensee
 - b. description: Station number: 5800312, Station name: Ploetzensee, Surface water: Ploetzensee
 - c. encoding type: application/geo+json
 - d. location:
 - i. type: Point
 - ii. coordinates: 13.330792, 52.5427025
4. datastreams:
 - a. name: Wasserportal Berlin - Water Level - Ploetzensee
 - b. description: Station number: 5800312, Station name: Ploetzensee, Surface water: Ploetzensee
 - c. observation type: http://www.opengis.net/def/observationType/OGC-OM/2.0/OM_ComplexObservation
 - d. unit of measurement:
 - i. name: meter
 - ii. symbol: m
 - iii. definition: <https://qudt.org/vocab/unit/M>
 - e. sensor:
 - i. name: Water level sensor in Ploetzensee
 - ii. description: In-situ water level sensor
 - iii. encoding type: text
 - iv. metadata: Station number: 5800312, Station name: Ploetzensee, Surface water: Ploetzensee. Longitude in UTM 33 N system: 386803, latitude in UTM 33 N system: 5822711
 - f. observed property:
 - i. name: water level
 - ii. definition: <https://smartdatamodels.org/dataModel.Environment/waterLevel>

¹⁸ In this section, the term “metadata” is used to record the description of a station of measurement and the variables and sensors used in that station. All these characteristics are stored in the Sensor Things API. In other parts of the project “metadata” is used for describing datasets in the project and stored as ISO 19115 documents in GeoNetwork.

- iii. description: Water level

The JSON file corresponding to the second dataset is the following:

1. name: Weid_Aqua100Data
2. description: Data from Weid Aqua 100 provided by KWB
3. locations:
 - a. name: Weidendammer Brücke at river Spree in the Berlin City Center
 - b. description: Weidendammer Brücke at river Spree in the Berlin City Center
 - c. encoding type: application/geo+json
 - d. location:
 - i. type: Point
 - ii. coordinates: 13.39, 52.52
4. multi datastreams:
 - a. name: Surface water conductivity in river Spree
 - b. description: Surface water conductivity in river Spree
 - c. observation type: http://www.opengis.net/def/observationType/OGC-OM/2.0/OM_ComplexObservation
 - d. multi observation data types: <https://qudt.org/vocab/unit/SEC>,
<https://saref.etsi.org/saref4watr/Temperature>,
<https://saref.etsi.org/saref4watr/Conductivity>,
<https://saref.etsi.org/saref4watr/TotalDissolvedSolids>
 - e. unit of measurements:
 - i. name: seconds, symbol: s, definition: <https://qudt.org/vocab/unit/SEC>
 - ii. name: temperature, symbol: C, definition: <https://saref.etsi.org/saref4watr/Temperature>
 - iii. name: specific conductivity, symbol: uS/cm, definition: <https://saref.etsi.org/saref4watr/Conductivity>
 - iv. name: total dissolved solids, symbol: ppt, definition: <https://saref.etsi.org/saref4watr/TotalDissolvedSolids>
 - f. sensor:
 - i. name: Probe AquaTroll 100
 - ii. description: In-situ AquaTroll 100
 - iii. encoding type: text
 - iv. metadata: Conductivity sensor (Probe AquaTroll 100) during summer 2016, installed close to Weidendammer Brucke at river Spree in the Berlin City Center. Time interval of measurements is 15 min. Besides Conductivity, the water temperature is measured, too. Suspended solids are calculated based on conductivity measurements.
 - g. observed properties:
 - i. name: seconds, definition: <https://qudt.org/vocab/unit/SEC>, description: Seconds since the first measurement.

- ii. name: temperature , definition:
<https://saref.etsi.org/saref4watr/Temperature>, description: Water temperature in Celsius
- iii. name: specific conductivity, definition:
<https://saref.etsi.org/saref4watr/Conductivity>, description: Conductivity at 25 Celsius water temperature in uS/cm
- iv. name: total dissolved solids, definition:
<https://saref.etsi.org/saref4watr/TotalDissolvedSolids>, description: The amount of total suspended solids, calculated from conductivity.

The JSON files were pushed to the FROST server. The complete URL to post the metadata to the server is <https://frost.iotlab.com/sensorthings/v1.1/Things>. In the request, the content-type header should be set to "application/json". The response returned by the FROST server is 201, meaning the correct creation of a Thing according to the received metadata.

The sending of data stored initially in CSV files was automated. The first step was to remove incorrect data from the CSV files. The CSV files were read in an automated way using the right charset and column delimiter; in the case of the Berlin pilot, the charset "windows-1250" and the character ";" Each column was individually retrieved and examined by the automated reading process. Furthermore, the timestamp format was also automatically transformed, matching the format used by the FROST server and the SensorThings API. The timestamp corresponds to the attribute "phenomenonTime" in the payload sent to the FROST server. The time zone corresponding to Berlin was added, too; the hour corresponds to the Zulu time. The measurement values are added to the attribute "result" payload. Finally, the sending of data is using a POST request to the FROST server, using an Observation for each set of measurements provided by a Datastream or a MultiDatastream as defined in the OGC SensorThings API specification.

The different tools used for the pilot in Berlin are available on GitLab:

- Berlin oxygen sensor: <https://gitlab.distantaccess.com/ad4gd/berlinoxygen>
- Berlin Wasser portal: <https://gitlab.distantaccess.com/ad4gd/berlinwasserportal>
- CSV reader for Weid Aqua 100 sensor: <https://gitlab.distantaccess.com/ad4gd/csvreader>

Of course, these tools will continue to evolve during the second part of the project. The project will ensure that the reuse of these tools by the different stakeholders will be possible, including after the end of the project.

Similar work has started since the beginning of the project and concerns the automated ingestion of data from diverse low-cost sensors used to measure air quality. This work is detailed in deliverable D6.1 as a preparatory activity for the pilot using air quality data. Low-cost sensors are commercialised by participatory science networks such as PurpleAir and Sensor.Community. However, some limitations were discovered: the main one is the variety of file formats employed when downloading the data from these community platforms. A prototype was designed and implemented to collect daily data from Plume Flow 2, EarthSense Zephyr, and Sensor.Community. It handles different kinds of data formats, for instance, CSV files. The

prototype also uses some automated processes to harmonise the heterogeneous data, notably through semantic mapping. The related work will continue in the second half of the project. The source code is available on GitHub: <https://github.com/AstonAirQuality/AirQualitySensors>.

The preliminary phase of the AD4GD project has demonstrated the need for a set of ingestion tools using the OGC SensorThings API to collect and store the data in the FROST/STA server. Initial versions of such tools were developed in the context of the small lakes in Berlin and the low-cost sensors measuring the air quality. These tools are also an efficient way to solve the issue of interoperability linked to the heterogeneous IoT data; indeed, all the data will become accessible through only one protocol, namely Sensor Things API.

A parallel attempt to import data into Sensor Things API was made in TAPIS¹⁹. In this case, the objective is not to automate data ingestion but to illustrate how this process can be done by combining CSV tables with semantic tagging in a generic way (See Figure 24) in a Javascript GUI interface. Converting these attempts into a generic tool that can cover most cases will be challenging, and the effort will continue in the second part of the project.

Figure 24: TAPIS import process.

10 SIMPL

In the context of the task related to the scalability and edge computing optimization, Simpl was studied during the first half of the project. Simpl is the smart middleware that will enable cloud-to-edge federations and support all major data initiatives funded by the European Commission, such as common European data spaces. Simpl is only software, but not the associated services or infrastructure. The provision of the software is only a sub-component of what it takes to make a

¹⁹ <https://github.com/joanma747/TAPIS>

data space a reality. The main characteristics to be implemented during the development of Simpl are the modularity (using the building blocks concept), the openness of its source code, the scalability, the security, and the interoperability. Based on the currently available documentation about Simpl, three categories of services will be implemented in the Simpl architecture: administration services, data services, and infrastructure connector services. The data services encompass the following functions: data and application sharing and discovery, data processing, and governance; furthermore, data orchestration and distributed execution will be supported. For the infrastructure, the services provided in the future will concern cloud and edge computing, HPC, PaaS, and infrastructure discovery. The services associated with the administration concern the following topics: federation management, security, network, audit, access control, trust, contracts, monitoring, and reporting. Finally, the governance in Simpl consists of support and CSIRT (Computer Security Incident Response Team). Simpl covers the federations at the infrastructure level, which is composed of the Internet of Things (IoT), edge, cloud, and HPC. These federations established in the infrastructure are used in ecosystems; the different European data spaces are part of such ecosystems. It means that data spaces are deployed on top of federated data infrastructures. The services offered by Simpl can be employed by the data spaces, particularly the Green Deal Data Space. Figure 25 illustrates the relationship between Simpl and the data spaces.

Simpl is a very new initiative procured by the European Union through two framework contracts. The first framework contract concerns the development of Simpl itself. Following a Call for Tenders in Spring 2023, this framework contract was awarded to 2 consortia in October 2023. For that reason, there are many unknowns on the actual implementation details of Simpl and the AD4GD will continue monitoring the evolution of the development of Simpl in the second part of the project and eventually test and adopt some of its building blocks as they become available

Figure 25: Simpl and data spaces.

Several potential risks concerning the expected Simpl middleware were identified in this task. First of all, the time schedule of the first release of Simpl is tight compared to the date of the AD4GD project termination. Indeed, the release of Simpl as MVP (Minimum Valuable Project) is scheduled in December 2024. The AD4GD project will finish on 31 August 2025. Then, it means there are only 8 months to eventually install, integrate Simpl in the GDDS architecture with some probable developments in the project and test the solution involving Simpl and the GDDS building blocks. Of course, in case of errors and bugs related to Simpl, the AD4GD partners involved in the technical parts need to report the problems to the Simpl development team and eventually to wait to solve the bugs for the next release of Simpl. This agile process can take an undetermined time until to obtain a reliable version of Simpl meeting the requirements and needs of the AD4GD project.

The technical maturity of Simpl was also identified as a critical risk for the new EU data spaces. Currently, it is not possible to assess the technical usefulness of Simpl due to the lack of maturity of the development. At the time of the writing of this deliverable, a review of the available source code published in the Simpl group²⁰ created on the GitLab managed by the European Union was done, but the source code available is limited to a proof of concept. Next expected release will consist of a Minimum Viable Product (MVP). The exam of the current release is inconclusive. In

²⁰ GitLab Simpl group: <https://code.europa.eu/simpl>

the same way, the technical documentation about Simpl, its completeness and quality are considered can also be a potential risk for the EU data spaces. Currently, the technical documentation is rather non-existent.

Another potential risk is the high ambition of the Simpl initiative. Indeed, the development of Simpl will be realised in a relatively short time taking into consideration that the Simpl MVP is expected at the end of 2024. A question may eventually arise if the ambition is not too high compared to the time scheduled for the development. Furthermore, the European Commission has put some pressure on the development of Simpl because the European Commission mentions in the next calls related to projects involving dataspace the use of Simpl. This can be also a potential risk to release too early Simpl for the future European project calls.

11 EDGE COMPUTING

Edge computing is referring to “a part of a distributed computing topology where information processing is located close to the edge, where things and people produce or consume that information” (<https://www.gartner.com/en/information-technology/glossary/edge-computing>). In the context of WP3, the data generated by the IoT sensors and devices can be handled at the edge, near the sensors (e.g., by the electronic circuits directly connected to the sensor and before transmitting the data to the cloud). The data processing is locally executed using the resources available at the edge. Edge computing avoids the utilisation of resources available on other parts of the infrastructure, typically on the cloud or the HPC. Thus, it reduces the need for a large bandwidth on the network.

For instance, a camera trap can be used in the pilot dedicated to biodiversity to detect and identify a representative of a given species. In this case, the picture that does not contain an animal or that contains a person can be discarded and never transmitted to the cloud. In extreme cases, pictures could not be transmitted as the important information to be collected and pushed to the cloud is the time of the observation and the species name. The cloud can be represented in the context of IoT by the FROST/STA server. So, pushing an image of the animal to the cloud might not make sense in this use case and also for performance reasons: indeed, sending an image consumes some bandwidth; on the other hand, only some little bytes are required to transmit the time of the observation and the species name. Furthermore, avoiding the sending of pictures is also a means to comply with the GDPR because an image can accidentally contain a person; if this image is not sent, no specific measure related to data privacy and protection is required in the cloud.

Another example is correcting errors in the data generated by the IoT sensors. Data processing consisting of filtering and correcting the data before sending them to the cloud is reducing the transmission and the amount of data between the edge and the cloud. In the case of the Berlin pilot, the IoT data is included in CSV files located in the Berlin Wasser portal. Each timestamp has one or several columns for the data generated by the IoT sensors installed in the small lakes. But when the data is not retrieved correctly, these columns are completed by the value “-777”. The data processing executed at the edge permits the removal of this data before sending it to the

cloud, which, in this case, is the FROST/STA server. This reduces, of course, the amount of data sent to the FROST/STA server. At the same time, a second edge data processing is also executed to convert the timestamp in a format compatible with the OGC SensorThings API. In principle, the edge computing resources could format the observations as STA entities and send them directly to a MQTT SensorThings API endpoint, avoiding unnecessary data transformations in the cloud and making the observations available in real time.

12 RESULTS

The metadata and the data available in Berlin for the small lakes were successfully pushed to the instance of the FROST server managed by IoT Lab. Retrieving the data stored now in the FROST server is possible through the OGC SensorThings API. The FROST server has two main sets of endpoints for the OGC SensorThings API:

- <https://frost.iotlab.com/sensorthingsapi/> and <http://frost.iotlab.com:8090/FROST-Server/v1.1>: The first URL is identical to the second one, but HTTPS was added with a Let's Encrypt certificate. This is, in fact, the entry point to reach the OGC SensorThings API enriched by the OGC APIplus extension. Each entity described in this report is accessible with HTTP GET requests.
- <https://frost.iotlab.com/sensorthings/> and <http://frost.iotlab.com:8090/FROST-Server/>: The same principle as above is applied with HTTPS and the certificate from Let's Encrypt. Both URLs provide a simple GUI to access other endpoints and an HTTP tool to create and execute requests to the OGC SensorThings API.

An HTTP GET request to <https://frost.iotlab.com/sensorthings/v1.1/Things> returns the list of all the "Things" entities currently stored in the FROST server managed by IoT Lab. For instance, the second dataset provided by KWB is entirely reachable through the URL [https://frost.iotlab.com/sensorthings/v1.1/Things\(26\)](https://frost.iotlab.com/sensorthings/v1.1/Things(26)) as shown in Figure 26:

```

{
  "@iot.selfLink": "https://frost.iotlab.com/sensorthings/v1.1/Things(26)",
  "@iot.id": 26,
  "description": "Data from Weid Aqua 100 provided by KWB",
  "name": "Weid_Aqua100Data",
  "HistoricalLocations@iot.navigationLink": "https://frost.iotlab.com/sensorthings/v1.1/Things(26)/HistoricalLocations",
  "Locations@iot.navigationLink": "https://frost.iotlab.com/sensorthings/v1.1/Things(26)/Locations",
  "MultiDatastreams@iot.navigationLink": "https://frost.iotlab.com/sensorthings/v1.1/Things(26)/MultiDatastreams",
  "Datastreams@iot.navigationLink": "https://frost.iotlab.com/sensorthings/v1.1/Things(26)/Datastreams"
}

```

Figure 26: Weid Aqua 100 sensor on the FROST server

[https://frost.iotlab.com/sensorthings/v1.1/Things\(26\)/Locations](https://frost.iotlab.com/sensorthings/v1.1/Things(26)/Locations) returns the information related to the location of the Weid Aqua 100 sensor as illustrated in Figure 27:

```
← → ↻ 🏠 🔒 https://frost.iotlab.com/sensorthings/v1.1/Things(26)/Locations
JSON Raw Data Headers
Save Copy Collapse All Expand All Filter JSON
@iot.count: 1
value:
  0:
    @iot.selfLink: "https://frost.iotlab.com/sensorthings/v1.1/Locations(25)"
    @iot.id: 25
    description: "Weidendammer Brücke at river Spree in the Berlin City Center"
    encodingType: "application/geo+json"
    location:
      type: "Point"
      coordinates:
        0: 13.39
        1: 52.52
    name: "Weidendammer Brücke at river Spree in the Berlin City Center"
    HistoricalLocations@iot.navigationLink: "https://frost.iotlab.com/sensorthings/v1.1/Locations(25)/HistoricalLocations"
    Things@iot.navigationLink: "https://frost.iotlab.com/sensorthings/v1.1/Locations(25)/Things"
```

Figure 27: Information about the location of the Weid Aqua 100 sensor.

An HTTP GET request to [https://frost.iotlab.com/sensorthings/v1.1/Things\(26\)/MultiDatastreams](https://frost.iotlab.com/sensorthings/v1.1/Things(26)/MultiDatastreams) allows the retrieval of all the data generated by the Weid Aqua 100 sensor. The different measurements are the timestamp, the water temperature, the specific conductivity, and finally, the total dissolved solids (see Figure 28).


```

← → ↻ 🏠 🔒 https://frost.iotlab.com/sensorthings/v1.1/Things(26)/MultiDatastreams
JSON Raw Data Headers
Save Copy Collapse All Expand All Filter JSON
@iot.count: 1
value:
  0:
    @iot.selfLink: "https://frost.iotlab.com/sensorthings/v1.1/MultiDatastreams(23)"
    @iot.id: 23
    description: "Surface water conductivity in river Spree"
    multiObservationDataTypes:
      0: "https://qudt.org/vocab/unit/SEC"
      1: "https://saref.etsi.org/saref4watr/Temperature"
      2: "https://saref.etsi.org/saref4watr/Conductivity"
      3: "https://saref.etsi.org/saref4watr/TotalDissolvedSolids"
    name: "Surface water conductivity in river Spree"
    observationType: "http://www.openais.net/def/observationType/OGC-OM/2.0/OM_ComplexObservation"
    observedArea:
      type: "Point"
      coordinates:
        0: 13.39
        1: 52.52
    unitOfMeasurements:
      0:
        name: "seconds"
        symbol: "s"
        definition: "https://qudt.org/vocab/unit/SEC"
      1:
        name: "temperature"
        symbol: "C"
        definition: "https://saref.etsi.org/saref4watr/Temperature"
      2:
        name: "specific conductivity"
        symbol: "uS/cm"
        definition: "https://saref.etsi.org/saref4watr/Conductivity"
      3:
        name: "total dissolved solids"
        symbol: "ppt"
        definition: "https://saref.etsi.org/saref4watr/TotalDissolvedSolids"
    Sensor@iot.navigationLink: "https://frost.iotlab.com/sensorthings/v1.1/MultiDatastreams(23)/Sensor"
    Thing@iot.navigationLink: "https://frost.iotlab.com/sensorthings/v1.1/MultiDatastreams(23)/Thing"
    Campaigns@iot.navigationLink: "https://frost.iotlab.com/sensorthings/v1.1/MultiDatastreams(23)/Campaigns"
    Observations@iot.navigationLink: "https://frost.iotlab.com/sensorthings/v1.1/MultiDatastreams(23)/Observations"
    ObservedProperties@iot.navigationLink: "https://frost.iotlab.com/sensorthings/v1.1/MultiDatastreams(23)/ObservedProperties"

```

Figure 28: Data from the Weid Aqua 100 sensor.

The different kinds of measurements realised by the Weid Aqua 100 sensor are available in details at [https://frost.iotlab.com/sensorthings/v1.1/MultiDatastreams\(23\)/ObservedProperties](https://frost.iotlab.com/sensorthings/v1.1/MultiDatastreams(23)/ObservedProperties) (see figure 29):


```

    https://frost.iotlab.com/sensorthings/v1.1/MultiDatastreams(23)/ObservedProperties
    JSON Raw Data Headers
    Save Copy Collapse All Expand All Filter JSON
    @iot.count: 4
    value:
      0:
        @iot.selfLink: "https://frost.iotlab.com/sensorthings/v1.1/ObservedProperties(14)"
        @iot.id: 14
        definition: "https://gudt.org/vocab/unit/SEC"
        description: "Seconds since the first measurement."
        name: "seconds"
        Datastreams@iot.navigationLink: "https://frost.iotlab.com/sensorthings/v1.1/ObservedProperties(14)/Datastreams"
        MultiDatastreams@iot.navigationLink: "https://frost.iotlab.com/sensorthings/v1.1/ObservedProperties(14)/MultiDatastreams"
      1:
        @iot.selfLink: "https://frost.iotlab.com/sensorthings/v1.1/ObservedProperties(15)"
        @iot.id: 15
        definition: "https://saref.etsi.org/saref4watr/Temperature"
        description: "Water temperature in Celsius"
        name: "temperature"
        Datastreams@iot.navigationLink: "https://frost.iotlab.com/sensorthings/v1.1/ObservedProperties(15)/Datastreams"
        MultiDatastreams@iot.navigationLink: "https://frost.iotlab.com/sensorthings/v1.1/ObservedProperties(15)/MultiDatastreams"
      2:
        @iot.selfLink: "https://frost.iotlab.com/sensorthings/v1.1/ObservedProperties(16)"
        @iot.id: 16
        definition: "https://saref.etsi.org/saref4watr/Conductivity"
        description: "Conductivity at 25 Celsius water temperature in uS/cm"
        name: "specific conductivity"
        Datastreams@iot.navigationLink: "https://frost.iotlab.com/sensorthings/v1.1/ObservedProperties(16)/Datastreams"
        MultiDatastreams@iot.navigationLink: "https://frost.iotlab.com/sensorthings/v1.1/ObservedProperties(16)/MultiDatastreams"
      3:
        @iot.selfLink: "https://frost.iotlab.com/sensorthings/v1.1/ObservedProperties(17)"
        @iot.id: 17
        definition: "https://saref.etsi.org/saref4watr/TotalDissolvedSolids"
        description: "The amount of total suspended solids, calculated from conductivity."
        name: "total dissolved solids"
        Datastreams@iot.navigationLink: "https://frost.iotlab.com/sensorthings/v1.1/ObservedProperties(17)/Datastreams"
        MultiDatastreams@iot.navigationLink: "https://frost.iotlab.com/sensorthings/v1.1/ObservedProperties(17)/MultiDatastreams"
  
```

Figure 29: Description of measurements thanks to the "Observed Properties"

More details about the sensor itself, including the related hardware and the metadata, can be found with the link [https://frost.iotlab.com/sensorthings/v1.1/MultiDatastreams\(23\)/Sensor](https://frost.iotlab.com/sensorthings/v1.1/MultiDatastreams(23)/Sensor) (see figure 30):


```

https://frost.iotlab.com/sensorthings/v1.1/MultiDatastreams(23)/Sensor
JSON Raw Data Headers
Save Copy Collapse All Expand All Filter JSON
@iot.selfLink: "https://frost.iotlab.com/sensorthings/v1.1/Sensors(30)"
@iot.id: 30
description: "In-situ AquaTroll 100"
encodingType: "text"
metadata: "Conductivity sensor (Probe AquaTroll 100) during summer 2016, installed close to Weidendammer measured, too. Suspended solids is calculated based on conductivity measurements."
name: "Probe AquaTroll 100"
Datastreams@iot.navigationLink: "https://frost.iotlab.com/sensorthings/v1.1/Sensors(30)/Datastreams"
MultiDatastreams@iot.navigationLink: "https://frost.iotlab.com/sensorthings/v1.1/Sensors(30)/MultiDatastreams"
    
```

Figure 30: Information and metadata of the sensor

The URL [https://frost.iotlab.com/sensorthings/v1.1/MultiDatastreams\(23\)/Observations](https://frost.iotlab.com/sensorthings/v1.1/MultiDatastreams(23)/Observations) gives access to all the data contained in the original CSV file. Each line of the initial CSV file is represented by an “Observation” entity as illustrated in Figure 31:

```

https://frost.iotlab.com/sensorthings/v1.1/MultiDatastreams(23)/Observations
JSON Raw Data Headers
Save Copy Collapse All Expand All Filter JSON
23:
@iot.selfLink: "https://frost.iotlab.com/sensorthings/v1.1/Observations(160)"
@iot.id: 160
phenomenonTime: "2016-06-16T20:00:00Z"
result:
  0: 18000
  1: 21.449
  2: 867.247
  3: 0.564
resultTime: null
FeatureOfInterest@iot.navigationLink: "https://frost.iotlab.com/sensorthings/v1.1/Observations(160)/FeatureOfInterest"
MultiDatastream@iot.navigationLink: "https://frost.iotlab.com/sensorthings/v1.1/Observations(160)/MultiDatastream"
Objects@iot.navigationLink: "https://frost.iotlab.com/sensorthings/v1.1/Observations(160)/Objects"
ObservationGroups@iot.navigationLink: "https://frost.iotlab.com/sensorthings/v1.1/Observations(160)/ObservationGroups"
Subjects@iot.navigationLink: "https://frost.iotlab.com/sensorthings/v1.1/Observations(160)/Subjects"
24:
@iot.selfLink: "https://frost.iotlab.com/sensorthings/v1.1/Observations(161)"
@iot.id: 161
phenomenonTime: "2016-06-16T20:15:00Z"
result:
  0: 18900
  1: 21.374
  2: 859.61
  3: 0.559
resultTime: null
FeatureOfInterest@iot.navigationLink: "https://frost.iotlab.com/sensorthings/v1.1/Observations(161)/FeatureOfInterest"
MultiDatastream@iot.navigationLink: "https://frost.iotlab.com/sensorthings/v1.1/Observations(161)/MultiDatastream"
Objects@iot.navigationLink: "https://frost.iotlab.com/sensorthings/v1.1/Observations(161)/Objects"
ObservationGroups@iot.navigationLink: "https://frost.iotlab.com/sensorthings/v1.1/Observations(161)/ObservationGroups"
Subjects@iot.navigationLink: "https://frost.iotlab.com/sensorthings/v1.1/Observations(161)/Subjects"
    
```

Figure 31: Observations made by the Weid Aqua 100 sensor

Concerning the first dataset provided by KWB, two “Things” are used for the same lake (Ploetzensee) but with different measurements (water level and water temperature) (see figure 32):

- Water level: [https://frost.iotlab.com/sensorthings/v1.1/Things\(37\)](https://frost.iotlab.com/sensorthings/v1.1/Things(37))
- Water temperature: [https://frost.iotlab.com/sensorthings/v1.1/Things\(38\)](https://frost.iotlab.com/sensorthings/v1.1/Things(38))

▼ 12:	
▼ @iot.selfLink:	"https://frost.iotlab.com/sensorthings/v1.1/Things(37)"
@iot.id:	37
▼ description:	"Water level from Wasserportal Berlin at Ploetzensee"
name:	"Wasserportal Berlin - Water Level - Ploetzensee"
▼ HistoricalLocations@iot.navigationLink:	"https://frost.iotlab.com/sensorthings/v1.1/Things(37)/HistoricalLocations"
▼ Locations@iot.navigationLink:	"https://frost.iotlab.com/sensorthings/v1.1/Things(37)/Locations"
▼ MultiDatastreams@iot.navigationLink:	"https://frost.iotlab.com/sensorthings/v1.1/Things(37)/MultiDatastreams"
▼ Datastreams@iot.navigationLink:	"https://frost.iotlab.com/sensorthings/v1.1/Things(37)/Datastreams"
▼ 13:	
▼ @iot.selfLink:	"https://frost.iotlab.com/sensorthings/v1.1/Things(38)"
@iot.id:	38
▼ description:	"Water temperature from Wasserportal Berlin at Ploetzensee"
name:	"Wasserportal Berlin - Water Temperature - Ploetzensee"
▼ HistoricalLocations@iot.navigationLink:	"https://frost.iotlab.com/sensorthings/v1.1/Things(38)/HistoricalLocations"
▼ Locations@iot.navigationLink:	"https://frost.iotlab.com/sensorthings/v1.1/Things(38)/Locations"
▼ MultiDatastreams@iot.navigationLink:	"https://frost.iotlab.com/sensorthings/v1.1/Things(38)/MultiDatastreams"
▼ Datastreams@iot.navigationLink:	"https://frost.iotlab.com/sensorthings/v1.1/Things(38)/Datastreams"

Figure 32: Things related to the Ploetzensee lake in Berlin.

The same principles are applied than the previously described dataset. The only major difference is the use of a “Datastream” entity because there is only one type of measurement by “Thing”. It also means that there is only one “ObservedProperty” per “Thing”, respectively water level and water temperature. The “Observations” contain only one result as displayed in Figure 33:


```

JSON  Raw Data  Headers
Save  Copy  Collapse All  Expand All  Filter JSON
  Subjects@iot.navigationLink:  "https://frost.iotlab.com/sensorthings/v1.1/Observations(9035)/Subjects"
  87:
    @iot.selfLink:  "https://frost.iotlab.com/sensorthings/v1.1/Observations(9036)"
    @iot.id:  9036
    phenomenonTime:  "2023-10-09T19:45:00Z"
    result:  122
    resultTime:  null
    Datastream@iot.navigationLink:  "https://frost.iotlab.com/sensorthings/v1.1/Observations(9036)/Datastream"
    FeatureOfInterest@iot.navigationLink:  "https://frost.iotlab.com/sensorthings/v1.1/Observations(9036)/FeatureOfInterest"
    Objects@iot.navigationLink:  "https://frost.iotlab.com/sensorthings/v1.1/Observations(9036)/Objects"
    ObservationGroups@iot.navigationLink:  "https://frost.iotlab.com/sensorthings/v1.1/Observations(9036)/ObservationGroups"
    Subjects@iot.navigationLink:  "https://frost.iotlab.com/sensorthings/v1.1/Observations(9036)/Subjects"
  88:
    @iot.selfLink:  "https://frost.iotlab.com/sensorthings/v1.1/Observations(9037)"
    @iot.id:  9037
    phenomenonTime:  "2023-10-09T20:00:00Z"
    result:  122
    resultTime:  null
    Datastream@iot.navigationLink:  "https://frost.iotlab.com/sensorthings/v1.1/Observations(9037)/Datastream"
    FeatureOfInterest@iot.navigationLink:  "https://frost.iotlab.com/sensorthings/v1.1/Observations(9037)/FeatureOfInterest"
    Objects@iot.navigationLink:  "https://frost.iotlab.com/sensorthings/v1.1/Observations(9037)/Objects"
    ObservationGroups@iot.navigationLink:  "https://frost.iotlab.com/sensorthings/v1.1/Observations(9037)/ObservationGroups"
    Subjects@iot.navigationLink:  "https://frost.iotlab.com/sensorthings/v1.1/Observations(9037)/Subjects"
  89:
    @iot.selfLink:  "https://frost.iotlab.com/sensorthings/v1.1/Observations(9038)"
    @iot.id:  9038
    phenomenonTime:  "2023-10-09T20:15:00Z"
    result:  122
    resultTime:  null
    Datastream@iot.navigationLink:  "https://frost.iotlab.com/sensorthings/v1.1/Observations(9038)/Datastream"
    FeatureOfInterest@iot.navigationLink:  "https://frost.iotlab.com/sensorthings/v1.1/Observations(9038)/FeatureOfInterest"
    Objects@iot.navigationLink:  "https://frost.iotlab.com/sensorthings/v1.1/Observations(9038)/Objects"
    ObservationGroups@iot.navigationLink:  "https://frost.iotlab.com/sensorthings/v1.1/Observations(9038)/ObservationGroups"
    Subjects@iot.navigationLink:  "https://frost.iotlab.com/sensorthings/v1.1/Observations(9038)/Subjects"

```

Figure 33: Observations for the water level

12.1 NEXT STEPS

One of the next steps consists of adding more datasets for the different pilots of the project. These datasets are generated by existing or new IoT sensors installed in the different lakes located in the city of Berlin. Other heterogeneous data can be pushed to the FROST server, for example, the data related to the local weather in Berlin. In the second half, the data generated by the two other pilots will be added to the FROST server, too. The IoT multi-protocol parser as a service is in charge of the harmonisation and interoperability of the different IoT servers deployed and managed by IoT Lab. The base of the IoT multi-protocol proxy as a service was designed and the related components were installed in the first half of the AD4GD project; one step further is to implement the final version of the multi-protocol proxy as a service. Furthermore, it is expected

to add user authentication and authorization on the FROST server instance run by IoT Lab; it will be done through a plugin to be installed within the FROST server. This plugin will ensure limited access to potentially sensitive data, notably for the protected species.

Another step is to make the Tools for Automated Ingestion of Data from Diverse Sensors general enough to make it exploitable after the end of the project by other stakeholders having similar needs.

13 CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The first half of the AD4GD project allowed the full examination of the concept of GDDS in relation to the Internet of Things. The design of the expected GDDS takes into consideration the requirements for the collection of data generated by heterogeneous IoT sensors and devices. Different servers were installed in the IoT Lab research infrastructure to study how to collect and integrate IoT data in the new Green Deal Data Space. On top of these IoT servers, the IoT multi-protocol parser as a service will take care of its final version of the interoperability and the harmonisation of the IoT data transmitted by the selected IoT communication protocols described in this report. Tools for Automated Ingestion of Data from Diverse Sensors are being produced to facilitate the exchange of data among the different data models and import formats.

Furthermore, the AD4GD project continues to follow the development of Simpl, concluding that the current version release does not allow for a concluding diagnostic. This is a risk for the implementation of the EU data spaces. The integration of IoT data generated in the three pilots (small lakes, biodiversity and air quality monitoring) is an important activity which continues in the second part of the project, with an emphasis on the IoT data harmonisation.

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